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1 **Temporal brain dynamics of the competition between proximity and shape**
2 **similarity grouping cues in vision.**

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4 Villalba-García, C ^{1,2}; Santaniello, G.^{2,4}; Luna, D. ³; Montoro, P.R.³; Hinojosa, J.A ^{1,2}.

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6 ¹ Facultad de Psicología, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain.

7 ² Instituto Pluridisciplinar, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain.

8 ³ Departamento de Psicología Básica 1, UNED, Spain.

9 ⁴ Departamento de Medicina y Cirugía, Psicología, Medicina Preventiva y Salud
10 Pública Inmunología y Microbiología Médica, Enfermería y Estomatología,
11 Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Spain.

12

13 Corresponding authors:

14 Cristina Villalba García.

15 E-mail: crisvi01@ucm.es

16 Tel.: +34 91 394 32 61

17 or

18 José A. Hinojosa.

19 E-mail: hinojosa@pluri.ucm.es

20 Tel.: +34 91 394 32 61

21

22 Instituto Pluridisciplinar, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain.

23 Facultad de Psicología, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain.

24 Paseo Juan XXIII, 1, Madrid, 28040, Spain.

25 Campus de Somosaguas, s/n, 28223 Pozuelo de Alarcón, Madrid, Spain.

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30 **Abstract**

31 Perceptual grouping operations are crucial for visual object recognition.
32 From the pioneering proposal of Gestalt psychologists, research has focused mostly on
33 the dynamics of single grouping laws. However, the integration between grouping cues
34 has received relatively less attention. The present event-related potentials (ERPs) study
35 aimed to examine the brain correlates of the competition between multiple grouping
36 cues (namely, shape similarity versus proximity) in visual patterns by means of a
37 selective attention paradigm that allows to measure the contribution of each cue
38 independently to the competition between them. Behavioural results indicated larger
39 interference effects of shape similarity on proximity cues when both cues compete.
40 ERPs data showed two main neural effects. First, the amplitude of a negative
41 component peaking around 250 ms (N200) was modulated by the interaction between
42 proximity and shape similarity cues. Specifically, the single shape similarity relative to
43 competing shape similarity cues elicited enhanced amplitudes. This finding seems to
44 reflect the visual salience and/or the processing fluency of the shape similarity grouping
45 factor. Remarkably, it can be considered an indirect brain signature of the competitive
46 interaction between grouping cues. Second, we found larger P300 amplitudes elicited by
47 single displays compared with competing trials, as well as by proximity relative to
48 shape similarity cues, which presumably reflects higher perceived confidence in
49 decisions during the processes joining perception to action.

50 **Keywords:** Proximity; Shape Similarity; Gestalt; Intrinsic principles; Competition;
51 Event - Related Potentials (ERP).

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60 **1. Introduction**

61 The principles of perceptual organization describe the mechanisms applied by the
62 visual system to extract the regularities that are present in our environment in order to
63 achieve meaningful representations of the world. In a first formulation, Wertheimer
64 (1923) described five principles: proximity, similarity, good continuation, closure, and
65 common fate. Within the last years, new principles of grouping have been described
66 (see Brooks, 2015, for a review). Additionally, Palmer (1999) proposed a
67 reclassification of grouping cues in two different clusters: intrinsic cues, based on
68 inherent relationships between the properties of the grouped elements (like size, colour,
69 position, etc.) and extrinsic principles, which require external elements to induce
70 grouping (e.g., common region or connectedness).

71 An important theoretical -and practical- issue that is receiving increased attention is
72 the study of the integration between different perceptual grouping factors to predict how
73 single cues interact when they are conjoined in the same pattern. Originally, the
74 grouping principles was formulated by the Gestalt psychologists as *ceteris paribus*
75 *rules*, so that they only can predict the perceptual output when *other things remain*
76 *equal* (Palmer, 1999). However, since natural images often contain many cues operating
77 simultaneously, it is necessary to determine the rules governing the combination of
78 different principles of perceptual grouping by means of experimental approaches.
79 Although the majority of studies have explored the relationships between intrinsic
80 principles like proximity, similarity or others (Ben-Av & Sagi, 1995; Claessens &
81 Wagemans, 2005, 2008; Kubovy & van den Berg, 2008; Oyama & Miyano, 2008;
82 Quinlan & Wilton, 1998; Schmidt & Schmidt, 2013; see Peterson & Kimchi, 2013, for a
83 review), a few recent studies have examined extrinsic principles (Luna & Montoro,
84 2011; Luna, Villalba-García, Montoro & Hinojosa, 2016; Montoro & Luna, 2015a;
85 Montoro, Villalba-García, Luna & Hinojosa, 2017). The study of the interaction
86 between grouping principles becomes especially relevant if we consider that human
87 beings must deal with challenging real environments that typically involve the
88 simultaneous operation of different grouping factors.

89 Prior studies have investigated competing grouping principles with the aim of
90 identifying the conditions that determine the dominance of a perceptual organization
91 over the other (Palmer, 2000, 2007; Quinlan & Wilton, 1998; Kubovy & Van den Berg,

92 2008; Luna & Montoro, 2011; Luna et al., 2016; Montoro & Luna, 2014; Rashal et al.,
93 2017; Schmidt & Schmidt, 2013;). Overall, evidence indicates stronger grouping effects
94 when two cues cooperate and weaker effects when they compete, compared to grouping
95 effects found for each single principle. Interestingly, there is also evidence suggesting
96 that when two grouping cues compete, the non-attended or non-dominant cue is
97 perceived to some extent (Luna et.al, 2016; Rashal et al., 2017).

98 Behavioural studies using phenomenological measures have reported weaker
99 grouping effects when proximity and similarity cues compete relative to grouping
100 effects found for each single principle. In contrast, the cooperation of these principles
101 enhances grouping effects (e.g. Quinlan & Wilton, 1998; Luna & Montoro, 2011). In
102 these tasks, it is noteworthy that participants provide subjective ratings of the grouping
103 strength for each trial, so their assessments could rely on cognitive rather than
104 perceptual judgements. A different approach has been to examine speeded visuomotor
105 processing of grouping cues during the competition between intrinsic grouping
106 principles. In the study by Schmidt & Schmidt (2013), the authors matched grouping
107 strength and still found differences in the processing of the distinct grouping cues. Thus,
108 it seems that subjectively equating two stimuli does not guarantee similar effects in the
109 visuomotor system. These authors concluded that their data reflect dissociation between
110 direct and indirect measures. In this sense, perceptual parameters determining grouping
111 strength would not be necessarily represented in the same manner by the
112 phenomenological perception and the visuomotor system. Interestingly, some authors
113 have argued that none of these measures predominates over the other and both could be
114 convergent measures of perceptual grouping (Kubovy & Gepstein, 2003; Palmer &
115 Beck, 2007). Therefore, it seems crucial to characterize and integrate measures from
116 different perspectives.

117 The high temporal resolution of event-related potentials (ERPs) makes this
118 technique suitable to track the temporal dynamics involved in the processing of
119 grouping principles (Razpurker-Apfeld & Pratt, 2008). Prior evidence from ERP studies
120 has shown differences in the time-course of the processing of proximity and similarity
121 cues (e.g., Han, 2004; Han, Ding & Song, 2002; Han & Humphreys, 2007; Mao et al.,
122 2004). In this line, proximity relative to shape similarity grouping cues have been
123 consistently associated with enhanced positive amplitudes around 100 ms over occipital
124 electrodes (P100), which has been interpreted to reflect an early representation of spatial

125 relationships between local elements (Han, Ding, & Song, 2002; Han, Song, Ding,
126 Yund & Woods, 2001; Han, Jiang, Mao, Humphreys & Qin, 2005b). Additionally,
127 larger amplitudes in central and parietal electrodes around 300 ms (P300) have been
128 observed for proximity when compared to similarity conditions. These effects seem to
129 indicate differences in confidence for perceptual decisions (Han et al., 2001). In
130 contrast, grouping by similarity relative to proximity has been associated with increased
131 amplitudes in an occipito-temporal negative component (N200) peaking between 240
132 and 340 ms. These effects are thought to stem from attentional post-perceptual
133 operations related to the discrimination and selection of stimuli features needed to
134 complete shape identification based on low-level factors (e.g., collinearity) (Han et al.,
135 2001, 2002, 2005a, 2005b).

136 Surprisingly, to our knowledge, only one previous study has directly examined the
137 brain correlates of the competition between Gestalt grouping cues. In an ERP study,
138 Han (2004) displayed stimulus arrays in which local circles and squares were grouped
139 into rows or columns based on either proximity or similarity. Half of these arrays
140 included proximity and similarity cues that were congruent in grouping local elements,
141 whereas these two cues were incongruous in the other half of the stimulus arrays. The
142 participants' task was to identify the orientation of these perceptual groups. An
143 interaction between both grouping cues was found between 180 ms and 220 ms over
144 posterior temporal-parietal areas. Larger negative amplitudes were observed for
145 similarity-grouping cues in the congruent compared to the incongruent proximity cue
146 condition. Remarkably, since the processing of proximity cues was not modulated by
147 congruency with similarity cues within this latency, the authors concluded that
148 proximity grouping-processes interfered with the processing of shape similarity
149 grouping. Additionally, proximity relative to similarity grouping elicited enhanced
150 amplitudes for the P100 and P300 components, although these effects were not
151 modulated by congruency. Interestingly, in the study by Han (2004), congruent arrays
152 included two single cues combined in cooperation, thus, it was not possible to examine
153 the contribution of single grouping cues to the competition between proximity and
154 similarity grouping. To overcome this limitation, in the current study, we have recorded
155 ERPs to explore the temporal dynamics of the dominance of single and competing
156 proximity and shape similarity cues. To this aim, we have used a grouping task recently
157 introduced by Luna et al. (2016). This new grouping paradigm is inspired by research

158 on dominance processing in hierarchical stimuli (e.g., Navon, 1981; Ward, 1983) and
159 enables the examination of the contribution of single grouping cues to the interactions
160 between grouping principles when they compete. The participants' task was to indicate
161 the position in the display (left or right) of groups based on two different cues by
162 selectively attending to one of the two perceptual groups while ignoring the alternative
163 organization based on the another cue. In two different blocks, participants were
164 instructed to attend to one of the two grouping cues (proximity or shape similarity)
165 while ignoring the other. Remarkably, this task allows testing the dominance of
166 grouping cues by examining the relative advantage of single cues and the interference
167 effects between competing cues. It can also be used to determine whether performance
168 on competing cues could be predicted by performance on single cues (Luna et. al,
169 2016). Considering all these characteristics, Luna et al.'s grouping task provides us with
170 a useful experimental tool to explore the temporal brain dynamics of the competition
171 between grouping cues, as well as the contribution of each single grouping factor to the
172 integration between Gestalt principles. Based on prior reports showing modulation of
173 the amplitude of a negative ERP component between 180 and 220 ms in posterior
174 electrodes (Han, 2004), we expect modulations within this time window under
175 conditions of competition between proximity and shape similarity grouping.
176 Specifically, Han (2004) found that the amplitude of this component in the shape
177 similarity grouping condition was larger for congruent relative to incongruent trials
178 while its amplitude in the proximity grouping condition was not influenced by the
179 congruency with shape similarity cues (Han, 2004). Based on this finding, we
180 hypothesize enhanced amplitude of this negative component in the single shape
181 similarity condition compared to the competing similarity condition, which would
182 provide a brain index of the interaction between Gestalt grouping cues. We also
183 hypothesize effects on the P100 and the P300 components elicited by single proximity
184 cues (Han et al., 2001). At a behavioural level, in the current study, we expect to
185 replicate prior results (Luna et.al, 2016). In particular, single displays should be
186 responded faster and more accurately in comparison to combined displays.

187 In sum, the integration between grouping cues is a crucial question in vision science and
188 the application of high-temporal resolution methods such as ERPs is especially
189 advisable to explore the temporal dynamics of the neural correlates underlying the
190 interaction between Gestalt principles. The present study aims to characterize the brain

191 correlates of the competition between two classical grouping factors (i.e. proximity and
192 similarity) by means of a paradigm designed to dissociate the single contribution of
193 each grouping cue and to measure the interference effect of the competing principles.

194

195 **2. Material and methods**

196 **2.1. *Participants***

197 Twenty-four students (12 females and 12 males) from the Universidad Complutense
198 de Madrid participated in the study for course credits. The age range was between 18
199 and 32 years (mean=20, 25, SD= 3, 06). Written informed consent was obtained from
200 each participant, and all of them reported normal or corrected-to-normal vision. The
201 research was conducted in accordance with ethical guidelines of the local committee
202 and conformed to the Declaration of Helsinki.

203 **2.2. *Stimuli and apparatus***

204 To make sure that the grouping strength of both cues was similar, we used stimuli
205 from Luna and Montoro's (2011) study ensuring that the visual angle and the luminance
206 value of the stimuli was equal to those of the that work. The stimuli display consisted of
207 seven elements arranged in a row. In the single conditions, the seven elements were
208 organized into two cohorts by means of a single grouping cue (proximity or shape
209 similarity): (1) four elements including the central element on one side (left or right) and
210 (2) the other three elements on the other side. In the competing conditions, the central
211 element could either be grouped by proximity or by shape similarity indistinctly. Thus,
212 if the central element was grouped by proximity with the elements on one side of the
213 display (left or right), then this central element was grouped by shape similarity with the
214 elements on the alternative side, in order to get a competition between grouped percepts
215 (Fig. 1). The shapes used were squares (11 mm × 11 mm) and circles (11 mm in
216 diameter) which subtended 1.0° at a viewing distance of 60 cm. The regular distance
217 between the elements was 3 mm (0.3°). In stimuli displaying proximity cues, the
218 distance between the target element and one of the flanker cohorts of elements was 9.5
219 mm (0.9°). The shapes were made of black lines (0 RGB) and presented on a white
220 background (255 RGB).

221 Six different stimulus arrays were constructed entangling grouping cues as well as
222 their mirror images for a total of twelve stimuli, divided into two sorts of displays:
223 single or combined in competition cues. In single displays, the central element could be
224 grouped with the elements on the left or on the right, based on only one grouping cue
225 (for example, grouping by proximity). In combined displays, the two grouping cues
226 always competed. Thus, the central element could be grouped with the elements on one
227 side of the display if grouping was based on shape similarity and on the other side if it
228 was based on proximity.

229 In each block, there were a total of eight different stimuli taken from the whole set
230 of twelve experimental stimuli. In shape similarity-directed blocks, there were two
231 shape-only displays (and their mirror images) and two conjoined competing displays
232 (and their mirror images). In proximity-directed blocks, there were two proximity-only
233 displays (and their mirror images) and two conjoined competing displays (and their
234 mirror images) (Fig. 1).

235 *****Figure 1 about here*****

236 The stimuli were presented on a 19-in. LCD-LED Samsung 943 N colour monitor
237 with a 75-Hz refresh rate, a 5:4 aspect ratio, and a resolution of 1024 x 768 controlled
238 by a personal computer running E- Prime 2.0 Professional software (Psychology
239 Software Tools, 1996-2002). Viewing distance was approximately 60 cm.

240 **2.3.** *Design and procedure*

241 The 2 x 2 design included two within-subject factors: Stimulus type (single or
242 combined grouping cues) and Directed attention (attention directed to groups based on
243 proximity or on shape similarity grouping cue). RTs and error rates were taken as
244 dependent variables.

245 Participants were tested individually in a quiet room. First, the ERP technique was
246 briefly introduced to the participant and informed consent was given. Then the
247 researcher proceeded to place the devices to use the ERPs. Once the participant was
248 ready to start the task, the instructions were provided making use of examples of
249 experimental stimuli displayed on the screen. The instructions provided to the
250 participants are reported in the Appendix A. In different blocks of trials, participants
251 had to selectively attend to groups based on one of the grouping cues whilst ignoring the

252 other, and to indicate whether the central element was grouped with the left or right
253 elements on the basis of the attended/directed grouping cue. For example, in proximity
254 directed blocks of trials, subjects were instructed to attend exclusively to groups based
255 on proximity and ignore those based on shape similarity indicating whether the central
256 element was grouped by proximity with the left or the right elements. On the other
257 hand, in shape similarity-directed blocks of trials, they were instructed to attend to
258 groups based on shape similarity and ignore those based on proximity. Each trial started
259 with a cross-shape fixation mark at the centre of the screen; 1000 ms later, a stimulus
260 was displayed at fixation for 200 ms and replaced by a blank screen that remained until
261 response. There was an intertrial pause of 800 ms. There were two practice blocks (one
262 for each attention condition: groups based on proximity or on shape similarity) and six
263 experimental blocks (three for each attention condition). The selection of stimuli was
264 randomized within blocks. The order of application of the blocks was counterbalanced
265 across subjects. Each experimental block consisted of 80 trials, whereas each practice
266 block consisted of 48 trials. There were 480 experimental trials in total, 120 trials for
267 each condition. Feedback was provided only in the practice trials. The task of the
268 participants was to indicate the position (left or right) of the cohort of elements grouped
269 by the attended grouping cue (either shape similarity or proximity) by pressing the left
270 (“Z”) or right (“M”) keys from the keyboard, making use of the index fingers of both
271 hands (left index finger for “Z” key and right index finger for “M” key) (Fig. 2).

272 *****Figure 2 about here*****

273 **2.4.** *Recording and pre-processing*

274 Electroencephalogram (EEG) activity was recorded through an ElectroCap cap with
275 Ag/AgCl electrodes placed at 60 scalp sites distributed homogeneously over the entire
276 scalp according to the 10-20 system (American Electroencephalographic Society, 1994).
277 Electrodes were referenced to the linked mastoids. The electrooculographic activity was
278 recorded using vertical and horizontal bipolar electrodes placed at supra-infraorbital
279 level of the left eye and on the outer canthus of both eyes, respectively. The EEG and
280 EOG were kept below 10k Ω . Recordings were amplified using BrainAmps amplifier,
281 continuously digitized at sample rate of 1 kHz and filtered online with a frequency
282 band-pass of 0.1–100Hz.

283 Analyses were conducted offline with software packages EEGLAB v.12.01 toolbox
284 (Delorme and Makeig, 2004) implemented in MATLAB (Mathworks, Inc.). Recordings
285 were down-sampled to 500Hz and filtered between 0.3 and 30Hz, using a basic FIR
286 filter (12dB/oct. roll-off). Epochs were created with duration of 1000 ms (starting 200
287 ms before stimulus onset and ending 800 ms after stimulus onset). Baseline correction
288 was applied on the post-stimulus interval using the 200 ms period prior to the onset of
289 each trial. Only correct response epochs were further analysed. Prior to artefact
290 correction procedures, epochs in which recordings at any channel exceeded $\pm 150 \mu\text{V}$
291 were automatically discarded. An independent components analysis (Makeig et al.,
292 1997) was performed to eliminate the blinks (Jung et al., 2000). Finally, epochs
293 contaminated with gross artefacts were rejected after visual inspection.

294 This procedure led to average admission of 82.91% (11.3) in proximity single trials,
295 82.21% (8.11) in proximity combined trials, 80.05% (9.72) in shape similarity single
296 trials and 81.41% (12.22) in shape similarity combined trials. Grand averages
297 waveforms were computed for each subject, experimental condition and electrode
298 location.

299 **2.5.** *Data analysis*

300 *2.5.1. Behavioural analysis.*

301 Data on RTs and error rates were subjected to separate analyses of variance
302 (ANOVAs) involving two factors Stimulus type (two levels: single or combined
303 grouping cues) and Directed attention (two levels: to proximity or to shape similarity).
304 Post hoc analyses were further performed with the significant level adjusted by the
305 Bonferroni method. Effect sizes were computed using the partial eta-square (η_p^2)
306 method. For the RT analysis, responses faster than 200 ms (anticipations) and slower
307 than 1500 ms were excluded from the analysis as outliers (0.25% of total trials). Also,
308 inaccurate responses were excluded (on average 3.92 %). All statistical analyses on
309 behavioural and ERP data were carried out using IBM SPSS Statistics (version 20).

310

311 *2.5.2. ERP analysis.*

312 Detection and quantification of ERP components that have been previously related
313 to the processing of single cues (P100 and P300) and the competition between
314 proximity and similarity grouping cues (N200) was carried out through a temporo-

315 spatial principal component analysis (PCA). The PCA has proven to be a reliable data-
316 driven method to isolate the components shaping an ERP waveform (Chapman &
317 McCrary, 1995; Dien, Beal, & Berg, 2005). The theoretical assumption underlying this
318 method is based on the fact that values from time-points forming a component tend to
319 vary in unison, whereas those that are part of the noise present a low covariance and
320 mutually cancel themselves since they behave randomly. Among PCA outputs, factor
321 scores are especially relevant since they are linearly related to amplitudes and may be
322 submitted to statistical contrasts.

323 First, a covariance-matrix-based temporal PCA (tPCA) was used to disentangle ERP
324 components over time. The main advantage of tPCA over conventional procedures
325 based on a visual inspection of the recordings and on ‘temporal windows of interest’ is
326 that it presents each ERP component separately and with its ‘clean’ shape, extracting
327 and quantifying it free of the influences of adjacent or subjacent components. Indeed,
328 the waveform recorded at a site on the head over a period of several hundreds of
329 milliseconds represents a complex superposition of different overlapping electrical
330 potentials. Such recordings can stymie visual inspection. In brief, tPCA computes the
331 covariance between all ERP time points, which tends to be high between the time points
332 involved in the same component, and low between those belonging to different
333 components. The solution is, therefore, a set of factors made up of highly covarying
334 time points, which ideally correspond to ERP components. A temporal factor score, the
335 tPCA-derived parameter in which extracted temporal factors may be quantified, is
336 linearly related to amplitude (Carretié et al., 2004; Dien 2010). The Promax rotation
337 system was used (Dien, 2010) and factors were rotated with a maximum of 100
338 iterations for convergence. The decision about the number of components to retain was
339 based on parallel analyses. As we will explain later, the ERP components associated
340 with single grouping cues processing (P100 and P300) and the competition between
341 proximity and similarity grouping cues (N200) was satisfactorily identified and
342 disentangled from other components.

343 Once quantified in the temporal domain, temporal factor scores were submitted to
344 spatial PCA (sPCA) to decompose the scalp topography of those components linked to
345 the processing of single and competing grouping cues. Whereas tPCA separates ERP
346 components along time, sPCA distinguishes ERP components along space, each spatial
347 factor ideally reflecting one of the concurrent neural processes underlying each
348 temporal factor. This spatial decomposition is an advisable strategy prior to statistical

349 contrast, because ERP components frequently behave differently in some scalp areas
350 than they do in others (e.g., they present opposite polarity or react differently to
351 experimental manipulations). Basically, each region or spatial factor is formed with the
352 scalp points where recordings tend to covary. As a result, the shape of the sPCA-
353 configured regions is functionally based, and scarcely resembles the shape of the
354 geometrically configured regions defined by traditional procedures. Moreover, each
355 spatial factor can also be quantified through the spatial factor score, a single parameter
356 that reflects the amplitude of the whole spatial factor. Retained factors were also
357 submitted to Promax rotation.

358 Finally, spatial factor scores (equivalent to traditional amplitudes, as
359 aforementioned) were analysed with repeated measures ANOVAs with the two-level
360 factors Stimulus type (single or combined grouping cues) and Directed attention
361 (attention directed to groups based on proximity or on shape similarity grouping cue).
362 The Greenhouse-Geisser (GG) epsilon correction was applied to adjust the degrees of
363 freedom of the F-ratios. Bonferroni- adjusted post-hoc tests were used to further analyse
364 significant main effects. Effect sizes were estimated using the partial eta-square (η_p^2)
365 method. The IBM SPSS Statistic (v.20) was the software used to carry out the analyses.

366

367 **3. Results**

368 **3.1. Behavioural data**

369 Mean RTs and mean accuracy (error rates) are shown in Table 1 and Figure 3. Analyses
370 on RTs revealed a significant main effect of Stimulus Type $F(1, 23) = 55.33$, $MSe =$
371 37617.2 , $p < 0.001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.71$. A significant interaction effect between Stimulus Type
372 and Directed Attention, $F(1, 23) = 7.91$, $MSe = 14683.4$, $p = 0.01$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.26$, was also
373 observed. The main effect of Stimulus type indicated that RTs for single trials (491 ms)
374 were shorter than those for competing ones (530 ms). The significant interaction
375 between Directed attention and Stimulus type indicated that the interference effect of
376 shape similarity on proximity cues (the difference between RTs to single and to
377 combined displays) was greater ($\Delta 65$ ms, $p < 0.01$) than the interference of proximity
378 cues over shape similarity ($\Delta 15$ ms, $p < 0.05$). Post-hoc comparisons between Stimulus
379 Type and Directed Attention, reported significant differences between proximity single
380 cues (476 ms) and shape similarity single cues (505 ms; $p < 0.05$), showing an

381 advantage effect of proximity: RTs for single proximity cue were shorter than those for
382 single shape similarity cue. In contrast, the comparison between both proximity (541
383 ms) and shape similarity (520 ms) competing conditions did not reach statistical
384 significance ($p > 0.10$).

385 Individual hit rates ranged between 90% and 100%. The ANOVA on accuracy data
386 showed a significant main effect of Stimulus type, $F(1, 23) = 24.84$, $MSe = 0.046$, $p <$
387 0.001 , $\eta_p^2 = 0.52$, indicating that participants were more accurate when the stimulus was
388 presented single (hits: 98%) rather than in competition (hits: 93%) (both $ps < 0.001$).
389 The analyses also reported a significant interaction between Stimulus type and Directed
390 attention, $F(1, 23) = 15.03$, $MSe = 0.006$, $p = 0.001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.40$. This interactive effect
391 showed that the interference of shape similarity on proximity cues (the difference
392 between errors for single and for combined displays) was greater ($p < 0.001$) than the
393 interference of proximity cues over shape similarity ($p < 0.001$). Pair-wise comparisons
394 with the Bonferroni correction found significant differences between all experimental
395 conditions (all $ps < 0.05$). Remarkably, these results mirrored those obtained with RTs.
396 There was no indication of speed–accuracy trade-off.

397 *****Table 1 about here*****

398
399 *****Figure 3 about here*****

400

401 **3.2. ERP data**

402 Figures 4 and 5 show a selection of grand averages in parietal and occipital scalp
403 electrodes where effects were observed. These grand averages correspond to parieto-
404 occipital (Fig. 4) and centro-parietal (Fig. 5) electrodes, where the critical experimental
405 effects were more evident. As we described in the introduction, the processing of single
406 grouping cues has been associated with positive ERP activity at posterior electrodes
407 peaking around 100 ms (P100) and 300 ms (P300), whereas the competition between
408 grouping cues have elicited modulations in a negative component at posterior electrodes
409 around 200 ms. After applying the tPCA, 7 temporal factors were extracted from the
410 ERPs. Figure 6 shows the factor loadings corresponding to these temporal factors. The
411 time course and peak latency of TF4 (peaking at 100 ms), TF3 (peaking at 250 ms) and
412 TF2 (peaking at 380 ms) clearly associate these TFs to the P100, N200 and P300

413 components, respectively (Fig. 4 and 5). Once the main ERP components of interest to
414 test the hypotheses of the current study with a data-driven procedure were identified,
415 further sPCAs were only performed for these effects, i.e.: TF4 (P100), TF3 (N200) and
416 TF2 (P300). This procedure allowed us to examine the topographical distribution of the
417 significant differences between conditions

418 *****Figure 4 about here*****

419

420 *****Figure 5 about here*****

421

422 *****Figure 6 about here*****

423 The sPCA decomposed TF4 (P100) in 6 spatial factors (SFs), the TF3 (N200) in 5
424 SFs and the TF2 (P300) in 6 SFs. The topography of each of these factors is
425 summarized in Table 2. Repeated measures ANOVAs on the SFs for Stimulus type (two
426 levels: single or combined grouping cues) and Directed attention (two levels: to
427 proximity or to shape similarity) were carried out as previously described. No
428 significant main effects or interactions were found for the P100 in any of the SFs.
429 Regarding the N200 a statistically significant interaction between Stimulus type and
430 Directed attention was observed in parietal and occipital regions (SF 1). The results of
431 post-hoc analyses indicated larger negative amplitudes for shape similarity cues in
432 competing relative to single displays. Interestingly, the lack of differences when
433 comparing proximity cues in competing and single displays indicates that this parieto-
434 occipital N200 might be an index of the interaction between grouping principles.
435 Finally, a main significant effect of Stimulus Type was found in central and parietal
436 regions (SFs 3 and 4) for the P300. Also, a main effect of Directed attention was found
437 at right central region (SF 4). Post-hoc analyses showed enhanced positive amplitudes
438 for single compared to competing conditions, as well as larger amplitudes for proximity
439 compared to shape similarity cues. Table 2 shows the results of these analyses. The
440 topography of the significant P100 and N200 effects is shown in Figure 7.

441 *****Table 2 about here*****

442

443 *****Figure 7 about here*****

444

445 **4. Discussion**

446 In the current study, we examined the temporal brain signatures of the dominance of
447 single and competing intrinsic grouping cues by means of two highly representative
448 grouping factors, namely proximity and shape similarity. In particular, we predicted that
449 the two competing principles would interact around 200 ms (before the stimulus
450 presentation), as reflected by the modulation of a negative component with a posterior
451 topography, in line with the results reported by Han (2004). To this aim, we used a
452 selective attention to grouping cues task that allows examining the dominance dynamics
453 of competing organizations: the relative advantage of single grouping cues and the
454 pattern of interference when two competing grouping cues are conjoined in the same
455 pattern (Luna et al., 2016). In the current study, we found that the effects of advantage
456 and interference show a dissociated pattern, which is in line with prior studies on
457 processing dominance (Amirkhiabani & Lovegrove, 1999; Lamb & Robertson, 1988).
458 Our behavioural results indicated a consistent pattern for both RTs and accuracy. An
459 advantage effect was found for proximity that was associated with faster and more
460 accurate responses relative to shape similarity when single cues were compared.
461 However, the interference effect between competing grouping cues indicated that
462 proximity was more interfered by the presence of shape similarity than vice versa. In
463 this line, we found faster and more accurate responses for single grouping conditions
464 compared to the competing condition. Interestingly, this interference effect was
465 bidirectional and asymmetrical since the magnitude of the interference of shape
466 similarity on proximity was larger than vice versa. Despite this asymmetrical interactive
467 effect, the results of our analyses suggested that the non-attended proximity cue was
468 still perceived and was not entirely suppressed, since the interference effect of
469 proximity on shape similarity was also statistically significant for both RTs and
470 accuracy. Thus, our data suggest that when more than one organization is possible in a
471 visual pattern, all the different perceptual alternatives are represented to some extent in
472 the visual system. Consequently, they compete for the dominance of grouping cues
473 (Luna et al., 2016; Rashal et.al, 2017). Similar results were observed in the study by
474 Luna and co-workers (see Exp. 1), although the interaction between factors only showed

475 a trend towards significance. The increased number of trials (480 vs 256 trials), as well
476 as the larger sample size (24 vs 16 participants) included in the current study compared
477 to the study by Luna et al. (2016) might partially explain differences in behavioural
478 data.

479 Previous research has found that grouping by proximity and by shape similarity are
480 associated with different time courses (e.g. Ben-Av & Sagi, 1995; Han and Humphreys,
481 1999) and distinct ERP correlates (e.g. Han, 2004; Han et. al, 2001, 2002). Studies
482 exploring interactions between intrinsic grouping cues reported larger amplitudes in a
483 positive component peaking around 100 ms in occipital electrodes for proximity
484 grouping cues (Han, 2004; Han et. al, 2001, 2002). This finding led the authors to
485 conclude that grouping by proximity depends on the representation of spatial
486 relationships between local elements, which are independent of visual features such as
487 the shape or the colour of discrete elements. To our knowledge, only one previous study
488 has examined the ERP correlates of the competition between shape similarity and
489 proximity (Han, 2004). An enhanced positivity between 100 and 140 ms for proximity
490 cues relative to similarity cues was found in this study. In contrast, we did not observe
491 amplitude differences between proximity and shape similarity in this time window. The
492 discrepant results might be related to differences in the configuration of the displays
493 used in both studies. In this sense, in the present study, we used the same stimuli in both
494 the proximity and the shape similarity competition conditions, so perceptual processes
495 were modulated by task demands in the absence of differences in the perceptual
496 organization of the displays. In contrast, Han (2004) displayed different stimuli in the
497 congruent and incongruent conditions, which could partially account for differences in
498 P100 amplitudes. Also, the grouping strength of the principles was not controlled for in
499 the study by Han (2004). In order to control this parameter in our study, we have used
500 the same stimuli as Luna and Montoro (2011), which reported no differences between
501 proximity and shape similarity cues in a phenomenological measure of grouping
502 strength. However, it should be noted that the matching of grouping strength was done
503 by a different sample of participants and previous studies have reported interindividual
504 differences in perceived grouping strength (Claessens & Wagemans, 2005).

505 Although null findings should be always interpreted with caution, our data suggest
506 that the early processing of proximity and similarity grouping cues share some aspects

507 when these principles compete. In fact, prior evidence has shown that the P100 might
508 characterize external properties of the stimulus regardless of the grouping principle
509 (Nikolaev & Van Leeuwen, 2004). Thus, in our study, similar P100 effects for the two
510 grouping cues might reflect the operations related to contour interpolation, which are
511 needed for the perceptual completion of squares and circles in both the shape similarity
512 and proximity competing conditions. In this line, P100 effects in posterior electrodes
513 have been reported during contour illusory processing (Murray et al., 2002; Nikolaev &
514 Van Leeuwen, 2004).

515 Remarkably, the first electrophysiological evidence of the interaction between
516 proximity and shape similarity cues peaked around 250 ms at parieto-occipital
517 electrodes. This rather middle latency effect is in accordance with prior proposals which
518 claim that when different configurations are in conflict, both grouping organizations are
519 processed equally until one of them dominates the perceptual interpretation of the
520 display (Rashal et.al, 2017). In agreement with the prediction based on Han (2004), our
521 results showed enhanced N200 amplitudes in the single shape similarity condition
522 compared to the competing similarity condition. In contrast, no differences in N200
523 amplitudes were observed between single and competing trials in the proximity
524 conditions. In the study by Han (2004), the interaction between proximity and shape
525 similarity cues modulated the amplitude of a negative ERP component between 180 and
526 220 ms in posterior electrodes (i.e. larger amplitude in congruent than incongruent trials
527 in the shape similarity block and no differences between proximity conditions; Han,
528 2004, p. 42). In line with these findings, our N200 effect could be interpreted as a brain
529 index of the visual salience and/or the processing fluency of shape similarity grouping.
530 Consequently, the enhanced amplitude elicited by the single condition may reflect an
531 easier processing of the shape similarity grouping cue when organizing the visual
532 pattern relative to the competing condition, which involves interference effects from
533 alternative grouping operations based on the non-attended proximity cue. Consistently
534 with this interpretation, previous research has reported that grouping by shape similarity
535 is reflected in a long latency occipito-temporal negativity within this time interval (Han,
536 2004; Han et al., 2001, 2002, 2005; Han & Humphreys, 2007; Mao et al., 2004).
537 Crucially, the modulation of this ERP component represents an indirect brain hallmark
538 of the competitive interaction between grouping cues, which could be explored in future

539 studies with other principles in order to determine how single grouping cues interact
540 when they are conjoined, especially in a competitive manner.

541 Finally, we found effects in a positive component peaking around 380 ms (P300)
542 with a centro-parietal distribution over the scalp. In particular, single displays elicited
543 larger positive amplitudes relative to competing displays in both proximity and shape
544 similarity conditions. Modulations of this component during single cues processing
545 have been previously related to integrative processes joining perception to action, which
546 reflect the operations that take place between the identification of the stimulus and the
547 selection of a response (Squires et al., 1975; Verleger et al., 2005). Additional evidence
548 for this view comes from the results of a recent study that reported an association
549 between perceived confidence in perceptual decisions and the P300 amplitude in a
550 visual discrimination task (Zizlsperger et al., 2014). Therefore, the larger P300
551 amplitude in our study may be associated with higher certainty in the perceptual
552 decisions made by the participants in the single trials relative to the competing condition
553 (see Montoro et al., 2015b). In line with this proposal, we also found shorter RTs and
554 more accurate responses for single compared to competing displays. Additionally,
555 proximity grouping cues elicited larger P300 amplitudes than shape similarity cues,
556 which is congruent with the finding of faster and more accurate responses for proximity
557 compared to shape similarity single cues. Interestingly, no P300 amplitude differences
558 between proximity and similarity cues were observed in the study by Han (2004), even
559 though speeded RTs for proximity relative to similarity displays were found. Taking
560 into consideration the divergence between ERPs and behavioural results, the author
561 provided an interpretation of his findings in terms of perceptual factors such as delayed
562 stimulus evaluation and categorization or motor factors such as slowed response
563 selection and execution (Han 2004, p. 43). In the current study, the similar pattern of
564 results found for the P300 amplitude and the behavioural performance argues in favour
565 of the association of this brain effect with confidence decisions during response
566 selection.

567 In sum, up to date research on the competition between perceptual grouping cues is
568 rather scarce. In the present study, we aimed to fill this void in research by examining
569 the temporal brain dynamics of the dominance of single and competing proximity and
570 shape similarity grouping cues. An important finding of the present study was the

571 modulation of a N200 component by the interactive effect between the grouping cues.
572 This electrophysiological correlate seems particularly sensitive to the perceptual fluency
573 of shape similarity cues and, indirectly, also reflects the interfering effect of the
574 unattended proximity cue in the competing condition. From a more general view, this
575 finding introduces a brain index of the integration between Gestalt grouping cues and
576 delimits the temporal occurrence of the competition about 250 ms after the stimulus
577 presentation, at least for the specific grouping factors studied. Besides, we reported an
578 enhanced posterior P300 for single relative to combined displays, which could reflect
579 higher confidence decisions related to response selection. Additional research is needed
580 to clarify whether the current findings generalize to other grouping principles, both
581 intrinsic and extrinsic.

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595 **Disclosure of interest**

596 The authors report no conflicts of interest.

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616 **References**

- 617 Amirkiabani, G. & Lovegrove, W. (1999). Do the global advantage and interference
618 covary? *Perception and Psychophysics*, *61*, 1308-1319.
- 619 Ben-Av, M. B., & Sagi, D. (1995). Perceptual grouping by similarity and proximity:
620 Experimental results can be predicted by intensity autocorrelations. *Vision*
621 *research*, *35*(6), 853-866.
- 622 Brooks, J. L. (2015). Traditional and new principles of perceptual grouping. In J.
623 Wagemans (Ed.), *Oxford Handbook of Perceptual Organization* (pp. 57-87). Oxford,
624 U.K.: Oxford University Press.
- 625 Chapman, R. M., & McCrary, J. W. (1995). EP component identification and
626 measurement by principal components-analysis. *Brain and cognition*, *27*(3), 288-310.
- 627 Claessens, P. M., & Wagemans, J. (2005). Perceptual grouping in Gabor lattices:
628 Proximity and alignment. *Attention, Perception, & Psychophysics*, *67*(8), 1446-1459.
- 629 Claessens, P. M., & Wagemans, J. (2008). A Bayesian framework for cue integration in
630 multistable grouping: Proximity, collinearity, and orientation priors in zigzag
631 lattices. *Journal of Vision*, *8*(7), 33-33.
- 632 Delorme, A., & Makeig, S. (2004). EEGLAB: an open source toolbox for analysis of
633 single-trial EEG dynamics including independent component analysis. *Journal of*
634 *neuroscience methods*, *134*(1), 9-21.
- 635 Dien, J., Beal, D. J., & Berg, P. (2005). Optimizing principal components analysis of
636 event-related potentials: matrix type, factor loading weighting, extraction, and
637 rotations. *Clinical neurophysiology*, *116*(8), 1808-1825.
- 638 Dien, J. (2010). Evaluating two-step PCA of ERP data with geomin, infomax, oblimin,
639 promax, and varimax rotations. *Psychophysiology*, *47*(1), 170-183.
- 640 Han, S., Song, Y., Ding, Y., Yund, E. W., & Woods, D. L. (2001). Neural substrates for
641 visual perceptual grouping in humans. *Psychophysiology*, *38*(06), 926-935.

642 Han, S., Ding, Y., & Song, Y. (2002). Neural mechanisms of perceptual grouping in
643 humans as revealed by high density event related potentials. *Neuroscience*
644 *Letters*, 319(1), 29-32.

645 Han, S. (2004). Interactions between proximity and similarity grouping: An event-
646 related brain potential study in humans. *Neuroscience Letters*, 367(1), 40-43.

647 Han, S., Jiang, Y., Mao, L., Humphreys, G. W., & Gu, H. (2005a). Attentional
648 modulation of perceptual grouping in human visual cortex: Functional MRI
649 studies. *Human Brain Mapping*, 25(4), 424-432.

650 Han, S., Jiang, Y., Mao, L., Humphreys, G. W., & Qin, J. (2005b). Attentional
651 modulation of perceptual grouping in human visual cortex: ERP studies. *Human Brain*
652 *Mapping*, 26(3), 199-209.

653 Han, S., & Humphreys, G. W. (2007). The fronto-parietal network and top-down
654 modulation of perceptual grouping. *Neurocase*, 13(4), 278-289.

655 Jung, T. P., Makeig, S., Humphries, C., Lee, T. W., Mckeown, M. J., Iragui, V., &
656 Sejnowski, T. J. (2000). Removing electroencephalographic artifacts by blind source
657 separation. *Psychophysiology*, 37(2), 163-178.

658 Kubovy, M., & Gepshtein, S. (2003). Perceptual grouping in space and in space-time:
659 An exercise in phenomenological psychophysics. *Perceptual organization in vision:*
660 *Behavioural and neural perspectives*, 45-85.

661 Kubovy, M., & Van Den Berg, M. (2008). The whole is equal to the sum of its parts: A
662 probabilistic model of grouping by proximity and similarity in regular
663 patterns. *Psychological Review*, 115(1), 131.

664 Lamb, M.R. & Robertson, L. (1988). The processing of hierarchical stimuli: Effects of
665 retinal locus, locational uncertainty and stimulus identity. *Perception and*
666 *Psychophysics*, 44, 173-181.

667 Luna, D., & Montoro, P. R. (2011). Interactions between intrinsic principles of
668 similarity and proximity and extrinsic principle of common region in visual
669 perception. *Perception*, 40(12), 1467-1477.

670 Luna, D., Villalba-García, C., Montoro, P. R., & Hinojosa, J. A. (2016). Dominance
671 dynamics of competition between intrinsic and extrinsic grouping cues. *Acta*
672 *Psychologica*, *170*, 146-154.

673 Makeig, S., Jung, T. P., Bell, A. J., Ghahremani, D., & Sejnowski, T. J. (1997). Blind
674 separation of auditory event-related brain responses into independent
675 components. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *94*(20), 10979-10984.

676 Mao, L., Han, S., Guo, C., & Jiang, Y. (2004). Neural mechanisms of perceptual
677 grouping in human visual cortex. *Chinese Science Bulletin*, *49*(8), 819.

678 Montoro, P. R., Villalba-García, C., Luna, D., & Hinojosa, J. A. (2017). Common
679 region wins the competition between extrinsic grouping cues: Evidence from a task
680 without explicit attention to grouping. *Psychonomic bulletin & review*, *24*(6), 1856-
681 1861.

682 Montoro, P. R., & Luna, D. (2015a). Does the relative strength of grouping principles
683 modulate the interactions between them? *The Spanish Journal of Psychology*, *18*, E33.

684 Montoro, P. R., Luna, D., Albert, J., Santaniello, G., López-Martín, S., Pozo, M. A., &
685 Hinojosa, J. A. (2015b). A temporo-spatial analysis of the neural correlates of extrinsic
686 perceptual grouping in vision. *Neuropsychologia*, *69*, 118-129.

687 Montoro, P. R., Villalba-García, C., Luna, D., & Hinojosa, J. A. (2017). Common
688 region wins the competition between extrinsic grouping cues: Evidence from a task
689 without explicit attention to grouping. *Psychonomic bulletin & review*.

690 Murray, M. M., Wylie, G. R., Higgins, B. A., Javitt, D. C., Schroeder, C. E., & Foxe, J.
691 J. (2002). The spatiotemporal dynamics of illusory contour processing: combined high-
692 density electrical mapping, source analysis, and functional magnetic resonance
693 imaging. *Journal of Neuroscience*, *22*(12), 5055-5073.

694 Navon, D. (1981). Do attention and decision follow perception? A comment on Miller.
695 *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, *7*, 1175-
696 1182.

697 Nikolaev, A. R., & van Leeuwen, C. (2004). Flexibility in spatial and non-spatial
698 feature grouping: an event-related potentials study. *Cognitive Brain Research*, 22(1),
699 13-25.

700 Oyama, T., & Miyano, H. (2008). Quantification of gestalt laws and proposal of a
701 perceptual state-space model. *Gestalt Theory*, 30(1), 29.

702 Palmer, S. E. (1999). *Vision science: Photons to phenomenology* MIT press.

703 Palmer, S. E., & Nelson, R. (2000). Late influences on perceptual grouping: Illusory
704 figures. *Perception & Psychophysics*, 62(7), 1321-1331.

705 Palmer, S. E., & Beck, D. M. (2007). The repetition discrimination task: An objective
706 method for studying perceptual grouping. *Perception & Psychophysics*, 69(1), 68-78.

707 Peterson, M. A., & Kimchi, R. (2013). Perceptual organization in vision. *The Oxford*
708 *handbook of cognitive psychology*, 9-31.

709 Quinlan, P. T., & Wilton, R. N. (1998). Grouping by proximity or similarity?
710 competition between the gestalt principles in vision. *Perception*, 27(4), 417-430.

711 Rashal, E., Yeshurun, Y., & Kimchi, R. (2017). The time course of the competition
712 between grouping organizations. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human*
713 *Perception and Performance*, 43(3), 608.

714 Razpurker-Apfeld, I., & Pratt, H. (2008). Perceptual visual grouping under inattention:
715 Electrophysiological functional imaging. *Brain and cognition*, 67(2), 183-196.

716 Schmidt, F., & Schmidt, T. (2013). Grouping principles in direct competition. *Vision*
717 *Research*, 88, 9-21.

718 Squires, N. K., Squires, K. C., & Hillyard, S. A. (1975). Two varieties of long-latency
719 positive waves evoked by unpredictable auditory stimuli in
720 man. *Electroencephalography and clinical neurophysiology*, 38(4), 387-401.

721 Verleger, R., Jaśkowski, P., & Wascher, E. (2005). Evidence for an integrative role of
722 P3b in linking reaction to perception. *Journal of Psychophysiology*, 19(3), 165-181.

723 Ward, L. M. (1983). On processing dominance: Comment on Pomerantz. *Journal of*
724 *Experimental Psychology: General*, 112, 541–546.

725 Wertheimer, M. (1923). Untersuchungen zur Lehre von der Gestalt. II. *Psychologische*
726 *forschung*, 4(1), 301-350.

727 Zizlsperger, L., Sauvigny, T., Händel, B., & Haarmeier, T. (2014). Cortical
728 representations of confidence in a visual perceptual decision. *Nature communications*,
729 5, 3940.

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745 **Appendix: A**

746 The instructions provided to the participants were the following:

747 *“In each trial, a fixation point will appear at the centre of the screen, in this case a*
748 *cross, towards which you should direct your gaze and keep it in that location. Then, at*
749 *the centre of the screen a row of seven elements will be displayed: circles and squares.*
750 *The central element will appear in the same position of that of the fixation point. The*
751 *central element can form a group with the three adjacent elements that are to the left or,*
752 *alternatively, with the three that are to the right. Look at this stimulus example [the*
753 *experimenter points out a single proximity stimulus on the screen]. You can perceive*
754 *that the central element is grouped with the three elements on the left because it is*
755 *closer to them than to the three elements on the right. Look at this other stimulus [the*
756 *experimenter points out a single shape similarity stimulus]. In this case, you can*
757 *perceive that the central element is grouped with the elements on the left because they*
758 *share the same shape (that is, circles) while the other three elements are different*
759 *figures (that is, squares). Now, look at these other stimuli [the experimenter points out*
760 *several competing stimuli], which have two competing ways of grouping the central*
761 *element with the adjacent elements because the central element is near to the elements*
762 *on the right but, at the same time, it shares the same figure (that is, circle) with the*
763 *elements on the left. In each block of trials, you will be informed of the grouping cue*
764 *that you have to attend in order to respond either proximity or shape similarity. A*
765 *practise block with feedback of your performance will be provided previously to start*
766 *the experimental task. Your task will be to indicate whether the central element is*
767 *grouped with the left or right elements according to the designated grouping cue while*
768 *ignoring the other alternative grouping cue. If the central element is grouped with the*
769 *three elements on the right you must press the keyboard key "M" with your right index*
770 *finger. If the central element is grouped with the three elements on the left you must*
771 *press the keyboard key "Z" with your left index finger. Only a single response is*
772 *accepted in each trial. You have to respond as quickly as possible without making*
773 *errors. Once you respond, the next trial will immediately begin with a fixation point*
774 *displayed on the screen. When you finish a block of trials, you will be notified with an*
775 *instruction screen and you could take a short break.”*

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777 **Figure Captions**

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779 **Figure 1.** Experimental stimuli and correct responses depending on the experimental
780 block. Each row of seven elements represents a stimulus. The correct response for each
781 trial is indicated by a hand pressing the correct key. The “Z” key indicates the grouping
782 of the central element with the three elements located on the left. The “M” key indicates
783 the grouping of the central element with the three elements located on the right. In
784 proximity single and proximity competition conditions, participants had to attend
785 exclusively to the cohort grouped by proximity and to ignore the shape similarity cue. In
786 shape similarity single and shape similarity competition conditions, participants had to
787 attend to the cohort grouped by shaped similarity while ignoring proximity factor.

788 **Figure 2.** Timing and sequence of events of an experimental trial. In a shape similarity-
789 directed block, the correct response to this stimulus was the “M” key pressed by the
790 right index finger. Alternatively, in a proximity-directed block, the correct response was
791 the “Z” key pressed by the left index finger.

792 **Figure 3.** Mean reaction times (ms), standard error bars and error rates (percentages) for
793 Directed attention (proximity vs. shape similarity) and Stimulus type conditions (single
794 vs. competition).

795 **Figure 4.** Top: Grand averages at parietal and occipital sites, where the experimental
796 N200 effects described in the text are visible. Bottom: Factor load after promax
797 rotation, temporal course and peak latency of the TF3(N200), which was extracted from
798 the temporal principal component analysis. TF: temporal factor.

799 **Figure 5** Grand averages of representative electrodes at central and parietal sites, where
800 the experimental P300 effects are visible. Bottom: Factor load after promax rotation,
801 temporal course and peak latency of FT2 (P300), which was extracted from the
802 temporal principal component analysis. TF: temporal factor.

803 **Figure 6.** Temporal principal component analysis: factor loadings after promax
804 rotation.: Temporal factors 4, 3, and 2 correspond to the P100, theN200) and theP300
805 components where experimental effects were predicted. TF: temporal factor.

806 **Figure 7.** Spatial factors extracted for the temporal factors 3 (N200) and 2 (P300)
807 through principal component analysis (sPCA). Only those spatial factors that were
808 sensitive to the experimental manipulations are shown. The color scale represents
809 spatial factor scores. The four experimental conditions are shown. TF: temporal factor;
810 SF: spatial factor.

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815 **Figure 1**

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830 **Figure 2**

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845 **Figure 3**

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859 **Figure 4**

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873 **Figure 5**

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887 **Figure 6**

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903 **Figure 7**

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917 **Table 1.** Mean reaction time (ms), mean accuracy (hit rate) and standard errors (in
 918 brackets), interference (Interf.) and advantage indices for each condition.

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	<i>Stimulus Type</i>					
	Reaction Time			Accuracy		
<i>Directed Attention</i>	Single	Comp.	Interf.	Single	Comp.	Interf.
Proximity	476 (73.7)	541 (120.8)	65	0.98 (0.13)	0.92 (0.27)	-0.06
Shape similarity	505 (75)	520 (68.3)	15	0.97 (0.17)	0.94 (0.23)	-0.03
Advantage	29	-21		-0.01	0.02	

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